

Scientific performance and research practices: Longer terms to evaluate higher risks

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Abstract

This manuscript presents an ongoing experience of impact evaluation applied to a recently created Brazilian research funding agency, the Instituto Serrapilheira (IS). Its purpose is to present the impact of this agency's research grant on young researchers' scientific performance and research practices. Longitudinal data collection involved survey, interviews, and information retrieval from CV Lattes and Scopus database and Scival Platform for both IS grantees and researchers not selected in the 1st Call for proposals issued by IS in 2017. The first analysis was a before-and-after comparison of both groups before and after the funding. Regarding the baseline, both groups had similar profiles, except for grantees having more international experience. Just after the project conclusion, there was little difference in their profiles. The second analysis was based on quasi-experimental research with an ex post facto design, having grantees as the treatment group and researchers not selected in the 1st Call as the control group. Some incremental effects were measured after the project's conclusion, indicating behavioral and research performance changes. Considering the nature of IS funding, scientific performance and research practices should appear as long-term impacts.

Introduction

This manuscript presents an ongoing experience of impact evaluation applied to a recently created Brazilian research funding agency. Its purpose is to present the impact of this agency's research grant on young researchers' scientific performance and research practices.

The Instituto Serrapilheira (IS) is a Brazilian private nonprofit organization created in 2017 to provide financial support to basic science projects and science outreach. IS brings innovation to the Brazilian scenario of science funding in at least five directions: i) it is the first family-philanthropically funded organization dedicated to supporting science in Brazil; ii) as a private institution, it provides researchers with greater flexibility in terms of resource allocation comparing to public funding agencies; iii) it is oriented to foster young researchers with high-risk and high-return research proposals, with emphasis on interdisciplinary, international collaboration in science, in line with funding schemes discussed by Heinze (2008), Franssen et al. (2018) and Lyall et al. (2013); (iv) it supports diversity in research projects, open science and science outreach practices; and finally (v) it stimulates network creation among grantees.

IS's first Call was launched in mid-2017 and was oriented to tenured young researchers (maximum ten years after Ph.D. completion, with a little compensation for women with

children) in the fields of hard sciences, including computer sciences, earth sciences, life sciences, engineering, physics, mathematics, and chemistry.

The first Call was quite competitive. It selected 65 out of 1.955 proposals from 331 different institutions from 26 out of 27 Brazilian states. The selection process involved 12 members of the Scientific Committee and more than 300 reviewers from Brazil and abroad.

The 65 selected researchers received one-year seed grants of up to a hundred thousand reais (about US\$ 27.000). Projects were initiated during the first semester of 2018 and finalized in the first semester of the following year. As foreseen in the 1st Call, in March 2019, the 65 grantees were oriented to propose a project extension of three years with a potential budget of a million reais (about US\$ 270.000). A peer review panel of 10 experts selected 12 grantees from the 65 to receive the additional funding. Projects were supposed to end by mid-2022, but because of the pandemic of SARS-COVID 19, they were extended to 2023 and 2024, which means that they are still active.

Just after launching its first Call for proposals, IS initiated a partnership with an external organization to build up and apply a methodology to measure the impacts of the overall research funding model, emphasizing the first Call. The research question that guides this manuscript is whether the financial support provided by IS and the procedures employed by the agency affect the scientific performance and research practices of its beneficiaries.

This article is organized into three sections in addition to this Introduction: The second section outlines data and methodology. The third section presents preliminary findings and a brief discussion. Finally, the study's main conclusions, implications, and limitations are presented.

Methods

The impact evaluation of IS 1st Call employed non-experimental and quasi-experimental research with ex post facto design. This section explains this research design, including data collection and analysis.

Data collection

Three datasets were created using information made available by IS of awarded and rejected individuals: 1) IS grantees (G), which encompassed the 53 grantees awarded by IS in the 1st Call and did not have additional funds; 2) IS grantees (M), which encompassed the 12 grantees awarded with additional funds by IS in the 1st Call; and finally, 3) NO grantees (N), which encompassed the 1.882 unsuccessful applicants to IS.

For individuals of the three groups, we collected primary data with a survey and retrieved information from Lattes Curriculum Vitae (Lattes) database. Lattes is a Brazilian database for scientific and technological information about students, professors, researchers, and professionals involved in Brazil's science and technology fields (Mena-Chalco & Junior, 2009).

Journal papers appearing in Lattes for a given scholar were matched with publication records retrieved from Scopus to extract bibliometric indicators in the Scival Platform. Matching was done through paper titles with a validation procedure to guarantee exact correspondence. Interviews with IS grantees (M) were done to understand context and operationalization of IS support.

Table 1 shows the main variables made available from IS, collected with the survey, and retrieved from Lattes for individuals from the three sets in each period (M1; M2; M3; M4 and

M5), as well as the bibliometric indicators from individuals' scholarly production extracted from Scival.

Table 1. Variables used in the evaluation

INDICATORS	VARIABLES	SOURCE PERIOD*	AND
Ethnic group	Description	IS M1	
Sex	Male	IS M1	
	Female		
Father's schooling	No schooling	Survey M1	
	Primary and Middle School		
	Secondary School		
	Tertiary education		
	Postgraduate studies		
Mother's schooling	No schooling	Survey M1	
	Primary and Middle School		
	Secondary School		
	Tertiary education		
	Postgraduate studies		
Nature of HEI – under graduation, master, and PhD	Public	Survey M1	
	Private		
HEI Brazilian Region - under graduation, master, and PhD	North	Survey M1	
	Northeast		
	Central-West		
	Southeast		
	South		
Year of termination – under graduation	Up to 2015	Survey M1	
Scientific Initiation during undergraduate	No	Survey M1	
	Yes. with a scholarship		
	Yes. without scholarship		
Ph.D. subject field	AGR agricultural sciences; BIO biological sciences; HEA health sciences; EXER exact and earth sciences; HUM human sciences. SOC social applied sciences; ENG engineering; INT interdisciplinary; LLA linguistics. literature. and arts	Survey M1	
International experience in academic stages - under graduation, master, Ph.D., and postdoc	No	Survey M1;	M2;
	Yes	M3+M4+M5	
Employment position	Description	Survey M1;	M2;
		M3+M4+M5	
Wage	Number of minimum wages	Survey M1;	M2;
		M3+M4+M5	
Research networks engagement	No engagement	Survey M1;	M2;
	Institutional network engagement	M3+M4+M5	
	National network engagement		
	International network engagement		
Diversity consideration in research teams	No	Survey M1;	M2;
	Yes	M3+M4+M5	
Use of open science practices	No	Survey M1;	M2;
	Yes	M3+M4+M5	
Engagement in science outreach	No	Survey M1;	M2;
	Yes	M3+M4+M5	
(For N dataset) Execution of project submitted to IS	No	Survey M2	
	Yes. with funding support		
	Yes. without funding support		

Research project execution with other IS grantees	No Yes	Survey	M2;
Journal papers published before submission to IS	Number	Lattes M1	
Journal papers published after submission to IS	Number	Lattes M2; M3; M4; M5	
Master supervisions before submission to IS	Number	Lattes M1	
Master supervisions after submission to IS	Number	Lattes M2; M3; M4; M5	
Doctorate supervisions before submission to IS	Number	Lattes M1	
Doctorate supervisions after submission to IS	Number	Lattes M2; M3; M4; M5	
Postdoc supervision before submission to IS	Number	Lattes M1	
Citations of journal papers	Number	Scival M1; M2; M3; M4; M5	
Field Weighted Citation Impact (FWCI)	the ratio of the total citations received by the denominator output and the total citations expected based on the average of the subject field	Scival M1; M2; M3; M4; M5	
Field Weighted View Impact (FWVI)	the ratio of the total views received by the denominator output and the total citations expected based on the average of the subject field	Scival M1; M2; M3; M4; M5	
Citescore Percentile	the relative standing of a serial title in its subject field (in %)	Scival M1; M2; M3; M4; M5	
Topic cluster prominence percentile	combination of three metrics to indicate the momentum of the topic: i) citation count in year n to papers published in n and $n-1$; ii) Scopus views count in year n to papers published in n and $n-1$; iii) Average CiteScore for year n	Scival M1; M2; M3; M4; M5	

* About data collection, retrieval and extraction moments:

M1 refers to the period between the end of the doctorate and project submission to the 1st IS public Call; data collection was done in 2018.

M2 refers to the period of execution of the projects contemplated in the 1st IS public Call (from 2018 to mid-2019); data collection was done in 2019.

M3 refers to the year after project completion for those that did not have additional funding from IS or the first year of project execution for those with additional funding from IS (from mid-2019 to mid-2020); data collection was done in 2020.

M4 refers to the additional year after project completion for those that did not have additional funding from IS or the second year of project execution for those with additional funding from IS (from mid-2020 to mid-2021); data collection was done in 2021.

M5 refers to the second additional year after project completion for those that did not have additional funding from IS or the third year of project execution for those with additional funding from IS (from mid-2021 to mid-2022); data collection was done in 2022.

** We highlight that in M1 and M2 survey was applied to G, M, and N individual's datasets, while in M3+M4+M5, it was only applied to G and M.

Grantees and no grantees before-and-after comparison

Once survey data was collected, we performed a before-and-after qualitative comparison regarding grantees (G and M) and no grantees (N) in moments M1 and M2. This analysis was oriented to find similarities and differences in trajectories between those awarded IS grants and those rejected in the 1st Call selection, considering the periods before and after IS research project submission. The idea was to identify if there was any selection bias in the group of young researchers that submitted to IS and the effects of IS grants in research practices of awarded and no awarded individuals.

In addition, we compared grantees with no additional funding (G) with those with additional funding (M) from IS in moment M3+M4+M5.

Table 2 shows the number and percentage of survey responses.

Table 2. Survey's responses

	Survey M1	Survey M2	Survey M3
Grantees with no additional funding (G)	53 (100%)	53 (100%)	44 (83%)
Grantees with additional funding (M)	12 (100%)	12 (100%)	12 (100%)
No grantees (N)	691 (37%)	299 (16%)	-

Quasi-experimental approach

Using survey data in addition to information gathered with IS and CV Lattes, we performed the matching procedures to define the treatment and control sample groups of the quasi-experiment. The quasi-experiment comprised IS grantees (G and M) as the treatment group and no grantees (N) as the control group. We used Propensity Score Nearest Neighbour (PSNN), matching 65 treatment units (IS Grantees) and 130 control units (no grantees).

The observable baseline control variables used in the pairing were: (i) Ethnic group; ii) Sex; (iii) Father's schooling; iv) Nature of HEI – under graduation; v) HEI Brazilian Region - under graduation; vi) Year of termination – under graduation; vii) Scientific Initiation during undergraduate; viii) Nature of HEI – doctorate; ix) Ph.D. subject field; x) Post-doctorate abroad; xi) Journal papers published before submission to IS; xii) Master supervisions before submission to IS; xiii) Doctorate supervisions before submission to IS; and xiv) Postdoc supervisions before submission to IS.

With the definition of the treatment and control groups, the analyses were conducted to measure the effect of IS on the average number of Journal Papers, Master supervision, and Doctorate supervision (of individuals) and Citations, Citescore Percentile, Field Weighted Citation Impact (FWCI), Field Weighted View Impact (FWVI) and Topic cluster prominence percentile (of journal papers).

Effects were tested by interaction in the Differences in Differences (Dif-in-Dif) model. This model serves to compare changes over time between treatment and control groups for a given variable of interest. In the analysis carried out here, for this temporal change, the “before” is considered as what occurred between 2012 and 2017 (identified in the Figures of next section

as the point “0”) and the “after” as what occurred between 2018 and 2022, or that is, after IS funding (identified in the Figures as point “1”). In this sense, we considered 10 years of observation.

Effects were estimated using the Generalized Linear Models (GLM) approach for weighted data, given the matching weights (Nelder & Wedderburn, 1972), choosing the link function and distribution family appropriate to the type of outcome/output indicator. Additionally, we provide a 95% confidence interval of our estimates, interpreting statistical relevance for effects according to Wasserstein et al. (2019). Data were analyzed using the software R.

As a complement to the Quasi-Experiment, an exploratory comparative analysis was carried out between the groups of grantees (G + M) and the group of denied (N) matched, directly using the functionalities of the SciVal platform. Table 3 presents the variables used in the analysis.

Table 3. Variables for comparative analysis in Scival

Variables	Source
Scholarly Output	Scival
International Collaboration (%)	Scival
Academic-Corporate Collaboration (%)	Scival
Field Weighted Citation Impact (FWCI)	Scival
Outputs in Top Citation Percentiles (top 10%, field-weighted)	Scival
Publications in Top Journal Percentiles (top 10% by CiteScore Percentile)	Scival
Citations per Publication	Scival
Outputs in Top Views Percentiles (top 10%)	Scival
Views per Publication	Scival
Field Weighted View Impact (FWVI)	Scival
Topic Cluster Prominence Percentile	Scival

Findings and discussion

This section presents preliminary findings and a brief discussion. Figure 1 shows the similarities and differences between IS grantees (G and M) and no grantees (N) concerning the period between the end of the doctorate and project submission to the 1st IS public Call. They have a similar profile, except for internalization issues, since IS grantees have more experience studying abroad and are more inserted in international research networks.

Similarities	Differences
1. Both groups had similar socioeconomic profiles (father's and mother's schooling achieved secondary school and tertiary education)	6. IS grantees had more international experiences than no grantees, mostly during doctorate and post-doctorate studies
2. Both groups mostly attended public HEIs in their academic stages	7. IS grantees are more engaged in international research networks
3. Both groups participated in intra-institutional and national research networks	8. No grantees are more involved with science outreach
4. Both groups declared limited concern about diversity in their research teams (about 33% of both groups)	9. 64% of no grantees (n=415) decided to execute the research project rejected by IS, half of them with other funding support
5. Both groups declared moderate use of open science practices in research (about 68% of both groups)	

Figure 1. Similarities and differences between IS grantees (G and M) and no grantees (M) in the period between the end of the doctorate and project submission to the 1st IS public Call

Figure 2 shows the main changes regarding the periods before and after IS submission for both groups. Few behavior transformations can be observed, such as a slight increase in diversity concern for both groups and science outreach practices for grantees and a slight decrease in open science practices.

Indicators	Changes from M1 to M2
Employment and wages	Individuals from both groups mainly maintain their employment positions with little wage increase
Diversity in research teams	Little increase
Open science practices	Slight decrease
Research networks	Individuals from both groups mainly maintain their participation; IS grantees more engaged in international research networks
Science outreach	Grantees overcome no grantees in science outreach engagement
Research among grantees	24 grantees reported joint research with other IS grantees

Figure 2. Changes observed in IS grantees (G and M) and no grantees (M) before and after IS grant

Table 4 presents IS grant's effects on different variables. Figures 3 to 10 show the effects for individuals in the G+M groups over time (between the "before" and "after" moments) showing the evolution of the treatment group (1, orange line) and control (0, blue line).

Table 4. IS effects on selected variables

Variables	IS Effect	[confint]		p
No master supervisions	0.533	0.335	0.850	0.008**
No Ph.D. supervisions	0.365	0.178	0.745	0.006**

Variables	IS Effect	[confint]		p
No journal papers	0.980	0.820	1.171	0.825
No citations per paper	1.122	0.992	1.270	0.068**
Citescore percentile	0.957	0.867	1.055	0.378
FWCI	1.002	0.887	1,117	0.967
FWVI	0,958	0.874	1.042	0.339
Topic Cluster Prominence percentile	1.064	1.019	1.110	0.004***

Source: Research data.

Figure 3: Effect of IS on master's supervision.

Figure 4: Effect of IS on PhD's supervision.

For the two supervision variables, the effect is negative, i.e., IS grantees (G+M) advise fewer master's and doctoral students compared to those denied (N) after having received funding. It is worth noting that in the baseline (until 2017), future grantees had more supervisions than future unsuccessful applicants. For the master's, there is a drop in guidance in both groups, although more pronounced for scholarship holders. For the doctorate, there is stability in the orientations of unsuccessful applicants, and a drop for grantees.

Figure 5: Effect of IS on number of journal papers.

There is no significant effect of IS on the number of publications. The two groups show a drop in production when comparing before and after. In this respect, it is also worth considering the pandemic effect, which in areas not related to health may have faced difficulties in carrying out research and, consequently, publishing. There is also another hypothesis, related to the drop in productivity of professors at the beginning of their careers (the case of groups G, M and N) who, when establishing a more lasting bond, end up taking on a set of tasks – mainly teaching and administrative – which they did not have to deal with during their doctorate and postdoctoral studies. In this sense, there is a relative decrease in the time devoted to research.

Figure 6: Effect of IS on number journal papers citations.

Regarding citations, it is important to explain that the model used, negative binomial, included adjustments for year of publication. This is because older publications tend to have more

citations than more recent publications, which brings biases to the analysis. In this sense, it is not strange to observe that the number of citations drops over time for the two groups, although the drop is smaller for grantees. There is, in this sense, a positive effect, albeit low (about 12%), indicating that publications by grantees are more cited than by denied researchers.

It is also necessary to consider that the IS has encouraged risky research. In this sense, the resulting publications tend to have a longer maturation time to be absorbed by the scientific community, leading to longer intervals to be cited in a meaningful way. This indicates the need to continue monitoring this indicator over time.

Figure 7: Effect of IS on Citescore Percentile.

There is no effect of IS in Citescore percentile, with no major change in the behavior of grantees and unsuccessful applicants in relation to the impact of the journals they have chosen over time, just as there are no major differences between the choices of the two groups.

Figure 8: Effect of IS on FWCI.

Figure 9: Effect of IS on FWVI.

There are also no effects of IS on the FWCI and FWVI indicators. Regarding the FWCI, both groups (G+M and N) show a decrease over time, which can be expected considering that there is a decrease in the number of publications and citations. As for FWVI, the behavior of group N is stable, with a small drop among grantees.

Figure 10: Effect of IS on Topic Cluster Prominence Percentile.

Finally, there is a positive, albeit low, effect of the IS on prominence, which means that grantees have published in areas of greater visibility than those denied. It is observed that there is an inversion of the positions of the two groups over time, which means that the grantees reorient themselves over time towards these themes.

The few IS effects or the absence of effects in the previous analysis must be seen with caution. Heinze (2008) pointed out that there is a tradeoff between short-term funded grants with more predictable and safer research questions and long-term research funding with expected higher impact.

Table 5 presents the additional data obtained for paired individuals from each group (G+M and N) over the period 2012 and 2022, with data collected in March 2023, directly in Scival. The

color intensities indicate the order of values for each indicator and year by group of individuals. The more intense the color, the higher the value.

Data corroborate some of the previous findings, about the IS effect on citations, but also brings some additional IS effects in related indicators, such as FWCI and Outputs in Top Citation Percentiles. There are also some effects on international collaboration and academic-corporate collaboration.

Table 5. Comparison between paired individuals from groups M, G and D for selected indicators from the Scival platform

		2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
Scholarly Output	M	25,0	21,0	24,0	30,0	16,0	31,0	29,0	28,0	47,0	60,0	39,0
	G	116,0	101,0	135,0	120,0	176,0	166,0	199,0	204,0	236,0	225,0	142,0
	N	160,0	228,0	223,0	244,0	301,0	294,0	375,0	377,0	424,0	482,0	298,0
International Collaboration (%)	M	68,0	42,9	66,7	70,0	62,5	67,7	75,9	60,7	51,1	55,0	43,6
	G	51,7	40,6	57,0	49,2	53,4	50,6	56,8	52,5	56,8	55,1	48,6
	N	42,5	41,2	47,1	40,6	45,5	51,0	51,5	46,9	42,5	41,5	43,3
Academic-Corporate Collaboration (%)	M	16,0	14,3	12,5	6,7	6,3	0,0	0,0	7,1	0,0	1,7	2,6
	G	1,7	0,0	2,2	0,8	2,8	2,4	5,0	2,9	1,7	2,7	3,5
	N	1,3	2,2	1,8	1,6	2,0	2,0	1,3	1,6	1,4	1,9	1,3
Field-Weighted Citation Impact	M	1,3	1,6	2,2	2,0	2,2	2,7	2,9	1,5	1,4	1,4	1,7
	G	1,9	1,3	1,7	1,2	1,4	2,2	1,4	1,2	2,0	1,4	1,7
	N	1,5	1,4	1,4	1,5	1,5	1,9	1,7	1,1	1,1	1,1	1,2
Outputs in Top Citation Percentiles (top 10%, field-weighted)	M	16,0	19,0	33,3	20,0	18,8	29,0	31,0	14,3	17,0	15,0	23,1
	G	19,8	12,9	19,3	10,8	17,0	18,1	14,1	11,3	16,1	14,7	17,6
	N	17,5	11,8	13,9	15,2	16,6	12,2	14,1	10,3	12,5	11,0	14,1
Publications in Top Journal Percentiles (top 10% by CiteScore Percentile)	M	43,5	52,4	26,1	57,7	56,3	35,5	55,2	39,3	50,0	38,3	53,8
	G	34,8	37,0	42,9	53,4	45,1	45,2	44,4	39,4	39,7	37,4	35,5
	N	34,6	33,2	28,7	39,7	31,9	47,6	28,6	33,9	31,1	32,6	27,9
Citations per Publication	M	37,7	51,2	64,3	41,5	38,5	38,8	27,3	21,9	15,2	9,2	2,4
	G	38,1	29,8	31,8	28,9	29,4	44,4	24,9	17,9	22,3	7,4	3,1
	N	45,1	41,9	36,5	37,6	30,9	44,0	30,3	15,5	11,5	6,5	2,0
Outputs in Top Views Percentiles (top 10%)	M	4,0	14,3	16,7	10,0	18,8	22,6	17,2	42,9	17,0	25,0	12,8
	G	26,7	16,8	26,7	15,8	30,1	35,5	23,6	25,0	26,7	20,4	28,2
	N	28,8	24,1	30,0	22,1	23,6	30,3	26,4	22,3	15,8	18,3	21,1
Views per Publication	M	33,5	37,8	36,3	31,3	37,8	39,7	35,8	40,9	27,1	23,4	16,1
	G	46,2	38,8	44,0	34,2	46,7	56,3	40,9	33,3	34,5	22,1	22,9
	N	46,7	48,7	46,9	42,9	44,0	53,0	38,4	34,3	26,6	23,4	16,1
Field-Weighted View Impact	M	1,1	1,1	1,6	1,3	1,4	1,8	1,8	1,5	1,1	1,2	1,3
	G	1,4	1,3	1,5	1,1	1,8	2,3	1,6	1,3	1,6	1,4	1,9
	N	1,5	1,5	1,5	1,7	2,0	2,3	1,8	1,4	1,2	1,4	1,4

Final remarks

Funding groundbreaking research is a desirable but not trivial task. Funding agencies worldwide know the importance of fostering new research fields and interdisciplinary efforts to address society's wicked problems. Nevertheless, science systems are restricted by funding arrangements primarily oriented to exploitation modes that lack institutional conditions to promote exploration trajectories (Franssen et al., 2018; Laudel & Gläser, 2014; Luukkonen, 2012). One crucial issue with these conditions is the use of traditional peer review selection mechanisms (Ayoubi et al., 2019; Boudreau et al., 2016).

Instituto Serrapilheira is a novel initiative in Brazil oriented to foster novel basic research done by young scientists. Beyond funding, the agency promotes research practices – such as diversity, open science, and science outreach, as well as flexibility in resource use, as a compliment to encourage new research paths.

The evaluation of Instituto Serrapilheira 1st Call involved comprehensive longitudinal strategies of data collection and analysis. So far, considering data collected until three years after the first round of research project's completion, we observe incremental behavior changes and incremental effects on their research performance.

We understand that it is too early to measure the impacts of this type of initiative and we reinforce the need for a systematic long-term evaluation for a better understanding of this new type of financing in the country.

Acknowledgments

Instituto Serrapilheira supported this study.

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